

A Certification approach for dynamic, agile and reUSable assessment fOr composite systems of ICT proDucts, servicEs and processeS

Welcome to the first Newsletter of CUSTODES, an EU-funded project aiming to provide trustworthy, cost-effective, agile and portable conformity assessment capabilities, to a variety of interested parties, covering multiple Assurance levels of Composite ICT products or ICT services.

In this newsletter, we proudly present a recap of our achievements as well as what is coming up! Enjoy and don't forget to follow us online.

Objectives

- ✓ • Promote the scalable, agile and verifiable certification of composite targets of evaluation (TOE), towards ensuring and fostering the protection, resilience of the ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes, converting Europe into a trustworthy certified digital ecosystem.
- ✓ • Facilitate the accurate definition, evaluation and classification of complex and highly interconnected (composite) TOE.
- ✓ • Optimise, automate and facilitate the conformity assessment of composite TOE ensuring compliance and mitigating potential compliance breaches.
- ✓ • Establish and guarantee the trust relationships in the certification process.
- ✓ • Enable robustness and sustainability of the self-assessment (i.e. audit/testing) throughout TOE lifecycles.
- ✓ • Promote and enable the trustable and transparent sharing and reuse of certification related information.
- ✓ • Development, validation and demonstration of CUSTODES framework through its application to large-scale real scenarios/ conditions - market validation and Roll out.
- ✓ • Provide tailored certification-related recommendations.

Pilots

Use Case 1

Cybersecurity Certification in 5G networks

This pilot has been designed to demonstrate how the CUSTODES solution can provide composite certifications for services through the re-use of certifications from multiple Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs).

Use Case 2

Ambient Intelligence for Smart Buildings/Homes

This pilot demonstrates how the CUSTODES solution can be used to facilitate conformity self-assessment of a composite ICT service/ ICT product as described within the regulation (EU) 2019/881 (The EU Cybersecurity Act).

Use Case 3

Cybersecurity Conformity Assessment Ecosystem for Startups/SMEs

This pilot has been specifically designed to demonstrate how the CUSTODES solution can support startups, micro and SMEs to implement cybersecurity conformity self-assessment or to increase their preparedness for cybersecurity certification for ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes.

Our Latest News

Scientific Publications

A taxonomy for cybersecurity standards

Deciphering Cyber-Security Certifications An Ontological Journey through Composite Systems and their certification

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Submitted Deliverables

D1.1 Project Handbook

D1.2 CUSTODES Data Management Plan

D2.1 CUSTODES Requirements Analysis

D2.2 CUSTODES Design and Reference Architecture

D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Events

The CUSTODES project has been actively participating in several events, showcasing its innovative approaches and strengthening collaborations within the industry. Here are some of the key events where CUSTODES has made its mark:

- **CYBERSECURITY MATTERS: How EU projects CUSTODES & CyberSecDome will protect European businesses**
- **Cybersecurity First! event**
- **EU Event (Policy, Cooperation and Collaboration): 8th ENISA - CEN - CENELEC - ETSI Cybersecurity Standardisation Conference 2024**
- **Arcadian IoT - SENTINEL Symposium & Showcase: Integrated and automated approaches for IoT Cybersecurity and Privacy Compliance**
- **EIT Digital booth at South Summit**
- **IoT Solutions World Congress / Barcelona Cybersecurity Congress**

The Consortium

The project unites 16 partners from 11 countries: Sweden, Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, Ireland, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Netherlands, Switzerland, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

Secure analytics for the interconnected world

KEY FACTS

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Topic:	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-04
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